

Appendix B: Figures

Fig. B.1: Target pixel files (TPFs) of each central star in the sample (marked with white crosses) obtained with `TPFPLOTTER`. The red circles are the sources of the *Gaia* DR3 catalogue in the field with scaled magnitudes (see legend). The aperture mask used by the pipeline to extract the photometry is also marked. Pixel scale is $21 \text{ arcsec pixel}^{-1}$.

Fig. B.1: continued.

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Fig. B.2: Periodograms of the known binary central stars Abell 46, DS 1, Abell 30, LoTr 5, NGC 5189, and NGC 2392. Grey horizontal dotted lines represent the False Alarm Probabilities (FAPs) at 10%, 1% and 0.1%.

Fig. B.3: Periodograms of those central stars which show significant variability in their light curves. Grey horizontal dotted lines represent the False Alarm Probabilities (FAPs) at 10%, 1% and 0.1%.

Fig. B.4: Periodograms of those central stars with no evidence in the MCMC analysis: Abell 7, Abell 28, JnEr 1, Abell 31, Sh 2-16, Fr 2-46, HDW 7, IC 5148/50, Lo 1 and EC 12390-1933. Grey horizontal dotted lines represent the False Alarm Probabilities (FAPs) at 10%, 1% and 0.1% .

Fig. B.5: Corner plots corresponding to the posterior distributions of the light curve modeling for targets with no or weak evidence in the 1-effect model. In each panel shows the marginalised posterior distributions of the orbital period and the amplitude of the model (A_{1E}) in the diagonal, while the 2D contour plot shows the dependency between both parameters. In the case of the amplitude (A_{1E}), we also include a vertical line showing the 95% percentile, that we assume as the upper limit for any periodicity testable with the TESS data.

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